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МАДАНИЯТ ВА САҢЪАТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ КУЛЬТУРА И ИСКУССТВО | JOURNAL OF CULTURE AND ART

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VOCAL TIMBRE IN SINGING FEATURES

ANNOTATION

This article will talk about the fact that vocal art is a special art, and when teaching students, classes will be conducted on topics in the published teaching aids and textbooks of professor teachers, strengthening students' knowledge in this field. And let's dwell on the features of the timbre of the voice when singing. The reason is that this is the main topic of our article, which we should try to illuminate in detail. Every student in the field of art should know the characteristics of the timbre of sound!

Keywords: vocal art, Music, Piano, opera art, composer, aria, vocalization, note, "ology" education, professional song.

QO'SHIQ AYTISHDA OVOZ TEMBRI XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Bu maqolada vokal san'atining o'ziga xos san'at ekanligi va talabalarni o'qitishda professor o'qituvchilarning nashr qilinayotgan o'quv qo'llanmalari va darsliklaridagi mavzularga doir darslar olib borilishi, talabalarning bilimlarini shu zailda mustahkamlash haqida so'z boradi. Qo'shiq aytishda ovoz tembri xususiyatlari haqida esa atroflicha to'xtalib o'tamiz. Sababi bu maqolamizning asosiy mavzusi bo'lib, uni atroflicha va bafurja yoritishga harakat qilishimiz kerak. San'at sohasidagi har bir talaba, ovoz tembri xususiyatlarini bilishi kerak!

Kalit so'zlar: vocal san'ati, musiqa, fortepiano, opera san'ati, kompozitor, aria, vokalist, nota, oloy ta'lim, professional qo'shiq.

ТЕМБР ГОЛОСА В ПЕНИИ ОСОБЕННОСТИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье речь пойдет о том, что вокальное искусство - это искусство само по себе, и при обучении студентов будут проводиться занятия по темам из изданных учебных пособий и учебников профессорско-преподавательского состава, закрепляющие знания студентов в этом направлении. А об особенностях тембра голоса в пении поговорим подробнее. Причина в том, что это основная тема нашей статьи, и мы должны попытаться осветить ее подробно. Каждый студент в области искусства должен знать особенности тембра голоса!

Ключевые слова: вокальное искусство, музыка, фортепиано, оперное искусство, композитор, Ария, вокализм, нота, алой образования, профессиональное пение.

The timbre of the singing voice is the most important characteristic of vocal art. Often the timbre of the voice is called its coloring. According to the timbre, vocal teachers determine the type of voice of the singer, the degree of his professionalism. The most important qualitative characteristic of the timbre of the voice is, first of all, freedom of the vocal apparatus when singing. Such qualities of timbre are also appreciated, such as resonant singing, roundness of vowels, smoothness of register transitions, sonority and flight of voice, close and high vocal position, singing vibrato, richness of timbre colors.

The infinite variety that we distinguish in the sound of the singing voice is the result of various combinations and changes in time of the main characteristics of the sound - the frequency of vibrations, the amplitude of vibrations and the overtone composition of the sound of the singing voice itself (pitch, strength and timbre of the voice) [1].

The peculiarity of the timbre of children's voices is that it varies depending on age according to the principle: the smaller the child, the poorer in number of overtones its spectrum. The special literature indicates four periods in the development of the voice of schoolchildren:

7-10 years – junior school age;

10-12 years – pre-amputation;

12-15 years old – mutational;

15-18 years – post-amputation.

It should be noted that all these age limits are very approximate and averaged, since in practice you can find many exceptions to the general rule. Nevertheless, a music teacher needs to know well the signs of each period of the development of a child's voice and be able to recognize them in the voices of his students in a timely manner.

Primary school age.

The sound of the voices of children of the first age group is usually characterized as light, sonorous, high, head, silvery, small in strength and range. However, these qualitative characteristics imply a certain aesthetic standard to which one should strive in the process of vocal work with children. In fact, among children who are not trained in singing, you can often hear a different sound: low, deaf, hoarse, chest, in the range of the a-zone of the speech voice or excessively tense and forced. At the same time the pitch arrangement of such voices is much lower than that of the first category of children with light and high voices.

Thus, it is possible to notice the presence of individual differences in children: some naturally have low, others have high voices. This is due to various trends in the predominant use of one of the natural voice registers - thoracic, or purely head (falsetto) [2].

With the development of the cerebral cortex of a child by the age of 7, his voice states the ability to mixed voice formation, which is advisable to consolidate in the process of vocal training. At the same time, the possibility of using pure registers in solving certain performance tasks is not excluded.

Tasks (search for a certain timbre sound of voices, correction of the quality of intonation, development of auditory-motor coordination in children-"gudoshnikov").

Practice shows that it is easier to achieve the correct pitch intonation with children when tuning voices to falsetto sound. Self the mechanism of falsetto sound formation reveals wider possibilities of sound-pitch adjustments in comparison with the thoracic mode of operation of the throat. For example, the vocal difficulties of children-"gudoshnikov" arise when singing using the thoracic biomechanism of phonation, which leads to the production of sounds only in a very narrow range (in the limit of the speech range, most often bordering within la-SIM or do-re1). When the child switches to a falsetto sound, there is a correction of intonation at higher sounds (la-si1 or do-fa2). This ability should subsequently be repeatedly consolidated with the student [3].

Striving for the timbral enrichment of the sound of the voices of primary school children, it is necessary to gradually form the skills of mixed voice formation. Other tasks are also relevant for the vocalist teacher: at a younger age, there are often significant speech defects (lisp, non-pronunciation of some consonants, etc.) that require correction, sluggishness of the articulation apparatus.

Pre-amputation period

The sound of children's voices in this period becomes more saturated in timbre. If they were systematically trained to sing, then during this period their voices reach their heyday. Their sound pitch and dynamic range increases significantly. The differences in timbre between sopranos (treble in boys) and violas become more significant.

The age of children 10-12 years is the most beneficial for the organization of a children's choir. His sound in this age period is distinguished by a wide variety of timbre colors, thanks to the possibility of using all voice registers

The mutation periods

At the age of 12-15, the child's body enters puberty. In this regard, there is a breakdown (mutation) of the child's voice. It passes most vividly and not infrequently painfully in boys.

The first signs of mutation of the voice should be considered the appearance of dullness of the sound of the voice, detonation, hoarseness, a feeling of discomfort in the throat when singing, disruptions of the voice on high notes, a decrease in the strength of the voice. According to psychiatrists and vocal teachers, the causes of mutation are the active growth of the larynx and vocal folds during this age period. The boys' voices go down: future basses have up to dom, future tenors have up to fam. The girls' voices, losing the top notes, fall by about a third.

The mutation in boys and girls proceeds differently: in boys it is more acute, in a leap, and in girls it is less noticeable, smoothly. The peculiarity of the mutation in boys also lies in the fact that during this period they experience not only detonation, but often a loss of coordination in the work of the a-gate vocal apparatus when singing. This is due to the fact that during the mutation period, boys lose the ability to mixed vocalization and their voice, as in early childhood, again splits into two natural registers (falsetto, which it sounds on the high notes of the first octave range, and the chest – on the low notes of the small octave, in a narrow range, approximately within a fifth)

Experts dispute the question: to sing or not to sing during mutation? Practice shows that moderate and systematic singing lessons with teenagers during the mutation period even facilitate and accelerate this process. It is important to follow the rule here: sing for a short time, softly and not high. It is also noted that the nature of the mutation depends on the previous singing development. If the child sang correctly before, then voice breaking occurs quickly and without complications. During the mutation period, special gentle exercises for the voice should be used. It is especially useful during the mutation period to strengthen the muscles of the vocal apparatus through breathing exercises, for example, A.N. Strelnikova (see description in the following sections of this manual) [4].

Post-mutation period.

During this period, we still observe residual mutation phenomena: unevenness of the sound of the voice over the entire range in timbre and strength, violations coordination in the work of the vocal apparatus, the newly appeared variegation of vowels, dullness of timbre, fatigue, etc. The voices of boys and girls, having passed the fracture, continue to form for a relatively long time in the process of maturation and growth of the whole organism. The development and strengthening of the adult voice are very gradual.

In the post-mutation period, the timbre of the voice is characterized by the spectrum of sound received at the mouth outlet, as a result of the transformation of the spectrum that arose at the level of the vocal folds, the filtering system, i.e., the resonant properties of the speech tract. The pattern of the spectrum depends mainly on the register biomechanism: thoracic, head (or purely falsetto) and various types of mixed. The quality of the timbre varies, acquiring different shades, depending on the predominance of the thoracic or falsetto mechanism.

Falsetto sound the singing voice is characterized by the poverty of the spectrum, although the quantitative characteristic of the falsetto sound is similar to the adult one, there are also some differences that relate to the amplitude characteristic reflecting the strength of the voice and the frequency of the main tone. The voices of young singers are weaker in strength and higher in pitch frequency than those of adults.

Chest sound as in adults, it occurs as a result of a complete oscillation of the entire mass of the vocal folds, however, in adolescence, the sound of a heavy voice is much poorer in the choice of overtones. Its quantitative assessment depends on many factors: age, type of voice, physical development, degree of training, work of the endocrine system, etc. However, the main factor is the age sign: the younger the singer, the fewer overtones in his chest voice [5].

Another point often causes controversy among experts: should children be taught to sing with vibrato? After all, its presence also indicates the sound quality of the singing voice. Based on physiological data, it can be argued that children can sing with vibrato at a fairly early age. Already among younger schoolchildren there are children with naturally set voices and children who, in the process of spontaneous singing, naturally (most often through imitation of good singing voices) come to the best and most convenient way of phonation for them. Nevertheless, choirmasters working with children often avoid singing with vibrato. Such a technique cannot always be considered necessary if we keep in mind the various stylistic features of the performance of vocal works or the tasks and rules of intonation in singing.

From the above it follows that the structure of the timbre of the singing voice in at any age, it is evaluated according to the main biophysical characteristics. However, the timbral sound of children's voices has its own characteristics that the teacher needs to know and take into account in his practical work.

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